

A NOTE ON THE 'KINETIC' EQUIVALENCE OF BROMINE ATOMS IN PHOSPHORUS PENTABROMIDE.

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Using radioactive bromine as indicator, it has been found that the five bromine atoms in PBr_5 are functionally equivalent.

Roginsky and Gopstein (*Phys. Z. Sowjetunion*, 1935, 7, 672) investigated the kinetic equivalence of bromine atoms in cupric bromide which decomposed when heated to the cuprous compound. They started with radioactive cupric bromide ($CuBr_2^*$) and effected its decomposition at 250° . The cupric salt was reformed at 100° in the presence of inactive bromine vapour. A 50% decrease in activity was obtained as a net result of such a series of steps. On repeating the cycle, however, five times, about 50% of the original activity still remained instead of about three per cent as is to be expected. Apparently, the bromine atoms in cupric bromide are not equally reactive.

The object of the present experiment was to test whether the above results are true for the phosphorus pentabromide molecule. It is well known that phosphorus pentabromide is formed by mixing theoretical proportions of phosphorus tribromide and bromine. On the other hand, when phosphorus pentabromide is heated, it melts to a red liquid forming a mixture of phosphorus tribromide and bromine at 100° , and the pentabromide is reformed on cooling. According to Baudrimont, if CO_2 be passed into a bulb containing the pentabromide heated to a water-bath, bromine passes off and the tribromide remains.

EXPERIMENTAL.

PBr_3 (7 c.c.) was shaken with about 150 c.c. of slow neutron-irradiated ethyl bromide. The ethyl bromide was removed by distillation and the radioactive PBr_3 remained as a residue. Its activity was measured by the liquid in a thin double-walled glass vessel and slipping it over a thin-walled G-M counter. Measurements were commenced when most of the 18 min. activity had decayed.

PBr_3 was next transferred to a glass vessel containing two side-tubes and cooled in an ice-bath. About 3.5 c.c. of Br_2 were added gradually, when crystals of PBr_3 separated out. The vessel with PBr_3 crystals was then heated on a water-bath at 100° , when PBr_3 readily decomposed into

PBr_3 and Br_2 . Br_2 was chased out by means of dry CO_2 and absorbed in a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide. The activity of PBr_3^* and $NaBr^*$ were then successively measured. It was found that the activity appearing in the compounds was roughly proportional to the weight of bromine atoms contained in PBr_3 and Br_2 . The reaction may be represented as follows :

where the asterisk denotes the radioactive constituent.

In a second series of experiments radioactive phosphorus pentabromide was prepared by exchanging PBr_3 with irradiated C_2H_5Br . Radioactive PBr_3 was then decomposed into PBr_3 and Br_2 , roughly proportional amounts of activity appearing in the compounds. This indicates that all the bromine ions in phosphorus pentabromide are functionally equivalent. A similar result has been reported by Grinberg (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U. R. S. S. Ser. Phys.*, 1940, 5, 342) who investigated the following reaction :

Incidentally, it was also found that if the compounds PBr_3 and PBr_5 are taken, containing equal amounts of bromine and are exchanged with equal amounts of neutron-irradiated ethyl bromide, the activity appearing in PBr_5 was much greater than in the case of PBr_3 . Measurement of activity in both cases was done in inactive ethyl bromide solution of same volume under practically identical conditions. Considering the difference in two cases, one may, therefore, suggest that the strength of chemical binding of bromine atoms in PBr_5 is greater than in the case of PBr_3 .

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